

Moving Beyond the Binary
A Case for Replacing the Complementarian-Egalitarian Classifications
with a Four-Quadrant Framework

A White Paper

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Executive Summary

This white paper argues that the binary classifications of complementarianism and egalitarianism have become insufficient as the standard categories for identifying Christian views on the redeemed male-female dynamic in the family and the church. While both classifications have legitimate historical, theological, and polemical value, they now function imprecisely, disregarding interpretive positions that do not neatly fit either side. As a result, Christians and churches are forced into classifications that inaccurately represent their biblical convictions and practical implications.

Rather than adjudicating the full biblical arguments for either position, this paper begins with the origin arc of complementarianism and egalitarianism to establish how these terms came to dominate. It then identifies the inherent problem within the current binary classifications: its tendency towards false dilemmas and hasty generalizations. Neither fallacy is intrinsic to the best forms of either position, but the binary structure's narrowness enables both. In response, this paper proposes a four-quadrant framework built around two interpretive axes:

Distinction–Non-Distinction and Limitation–Open. This framework preserves the theological crux of both complementarianism and egalitarianism while providing more sufficient categories for viable evangelical interpretations. The proposed interpretive positions for these quadrants, terminology aside, are believed to better account for the actual range of Christian belief and practice on this subject. Overall, the aim is to improve interpretive classification, not challenge interpretive conclusions. Churches, denominations, and affiliate networks must define the parameters of cooperation, but they should do so with categories clear enough to identify where Christians actually agree, disagree, and can faithfully participate together.

Introduction

For fifteen years now, afforded by pastoral ministry, I have had numerous biblical and social conversations in various settings with ordinary believers, church leaders, and seminarians about women’s roles and limitations. Over these years, in denominational and non-denominational life, I have discovered that more and more Christians do not neatly fit into the two classifications of complementarianism and egalitarianism. Until recently, when discussing the scope of women’s roles, positions, and participation, I would often describe a sliding scale between the two to help identify where someone may align: (far right) ardent complementarian, (middle right) moderate (or semi-) complementarian, (middle left) moderate (or semi-) egalitarian, (far left) ardent egalitarian.

Egalitarianism		Complementarianism	
Far Left	Middle Left	Middle Right	Far Right
Ardent Egalitarian	Moderate (or Semi-) Egalitarian	Moderate (or Semi-) Complementarian	Ardent Complementarian

Figure 1

This sliding scale has often sufficed for my audiences and ministry circles, but that was only a small sample size. Definitely not enough to turn the tide, and today I realize even if it had gained momentum, it would not have been sufficient to change the standard. Insofar as what can be seen, heard, and read within American Christianity, the issue of women’s roles and limitations has remained atop the national evangelical conversation without any apparent satisfying solution. I submit this is due to many on both sides responding to the extremes, either fear of becoming all-inclusive via egalitarianism or fear of proliferating male chauvinism via complementarianism.¹ Furthermore, denominational decisions and debates, including their splits—if not primarily, in part, about women’s roles in church polity and biblical positions on

¹ Here is an example from both sides: Colin Smothers, “Is the Slippery Slope Actually Slippery? Egalitarianism and the Open-and-Affirming Position,” 9Marks, November 23, 2019, <https://www.9marks.org/article/is-the-slippery-slope-actually-slippery-egalitarianism-and-the-open-and-affirming-position/>. Jennifer McKinney, “American Evangelism and Complementarianism: Authority and Abuse,” *Oxford University Press Blog*, May 15th 2023, <https://blog.oup.com/2023/05/american-evangelism-and-complementarianism-authority-and-abuse/>.

sexuality—have continued to oxygenate the flames of this subject, along with social media’s dissemination acting as gasoline.

These two classifications are not the cause of the interpretive differences or their extremes, but the question must be asked: Aside from sin, are they the cause of increasing debates and rifts because of their imprecision and absorption of other viable interpretive views? I say yes. Of course, this begs the question: Will more classifications not also multiply debates and rifts, or open the door to more niche positions? Possibly. Or perhaps a broader interpretive perspective may clarify who is and is not debating one another, and who can find common ground and fellowship agreeably, with or without separation. Thus, because the binary categories of complementarianism and egalitarianism function as imprecise classifications, I propose that they be replaced as the standard with a four-quadrant framework that better accounts for alternative interpretations of authority and functions within the redeemed male-female dynamic in the family and the church.² In this paper, I will not deal with the biblical arguments. The aim is to begin with the origin arc of these classifications to establish an objective understanding of why they are the standard, then explore the inherent problem, and finally present an alternative solvent that maintains the theological crux of both while accounting for interpretive and implicative diversity.

The Origins of Complementarianism and Egalitarianism

Complementarian and egalitarian are modern terms, though the concepts are historical. Complementarian is a neologism from 1987-1988. It was coined to categorize the theological position of the Danvers Statement and the newly formed Council on Biblical Manhood and Womanhood (CBMW), which emerged in response to secular feminism’s influence among Christians during the 1970s-1980s.³ John Piper and Wayne Grudem, in “Recovering Biblical Manhood and Womanhood,” explain that “complementarian” was originally constituted as an alternative Christian nomenclature to the “traditionalist” or “hierarchalist” labels and

² In this paper, aside from titles and quotations, “church” refers to local churches and “Church” refers to the universal Body of Christ.

³ “The Danvers Statement,” The Council on Biblical Manhood and Womanhood, archived November 1988, <https://cbmw.org/about/the-danvers-statement/>. “Vision & Mission,” The Council on Biblical Manhood and Womanhood, accessed June 2026, <https://cbmw.org/about/vision-mission/>. Denny Burk, “Complementarianism? What’s in a name?”, *Denny Burk* (blog), June 20, 2019, <https://www.dennyburk.com/complementarianism-whats-in-a-name-2/>.

perspective.⁴ The original group, and corresponding signatories, felt strongly they were combating an ideology that was not a mere blurring of the lines in championing equality, but a besieging of the biblical (and healthy) distinction of manhood and womanhood—of maleness and femaleness—for gender equivalence, and an erasure of sacred sexuality for autonomous sexuality. This context is more than a valid reason to present a polemical response. Egalitarian, as a neologism, is of French origin from equality (*égalité, égalitaire*), and arrived in the 1700s with its usage developing over time, approximately the 1870s-1930s.⁵ All of which percolated from socio-political movements for equality starting with philosopher Jean-Jacques Rousseau during the Enlightenment through the French Revolution with Mary Wollstonecraft advocating for women.⁶ Egalitarian originally articulated social equality among people and classes “as the chief value of a just political system.”⁷ Egalitarianism, building on its origin, finds its earliest usage among Christians in the 1970s and then becomes advocated by Christians for Biblical Equality (CBE) in 1987, a polemical counterresponse to complementarianism.⁸

The concepts of these two classifications date back as far as the fourth century and throughout the fifteenth to seventeenth centuries. Complementarianism, at its baseline doctrinal view, upholds that Scripture identifies five claims regarding the correlation of men and women in dignity, sexuality, the family, and the church: One, men (male) and women (female) are the two biological sexes and established genders created in God’s image with equal and inherent dignity and value (Genesis 1:26-27). Two, men and women are not interchangeable in every role—e.g., husband-wife, father-mother (1 Corinthians 11:2-12, Colossians 3:18-21, 1 Peter 3:1-7). Three, God’s ordained marriage is only between a man and a woman, and husbands have a God-appointed headship role in marriage—male headship-authority is not superiority; it is Christlike leadership (Genesis 2:15-24, Ephesians 5:22-33). Four, God reserves certain governing offices in the church solely for qualified men, not to the diminution of women but for order (Acts 1:15-26, 1 Cor. 14:26-40, 1 Timothy 2:8-3:10, Titus 1:5-9). Five, these distinctions

⁴ John Piper and Wayne Grudem, eds., *Recovering Biblical Manhood & Womanhood: A Response to Evangelical Feminism* (Wheaton, Illinois: Crossway, 2021), 15.

⁵ *Oxford English Dictionary*, “égalité (n.)” December 2024, <https://doi.org/10.1093/OED/2283492750>. Juliana Bidanure and David Axelsen, “Egalitarianism,” *The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy* (Spring 2025 Edition), <https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/spr2025/entries/egalitarianism/>.

⁶ Bidanure and Axelsen, “Egalitarianism.”

⁷ *Ibid.*

⁸ Donald W. Dayton and Thomas Howard, “A Dialogue on Women, Hierarchy, and Equality,” *Sojourners*, May 1975, <https://sojo.net/magazine/may-1975/dialogue-women-hierarchy-and-equality>. “History of CBE,” CBE International, accessed June 2026, https://www.cbeinternational.org/primary_page/history-of-cbe/.

are established at the beginning of creation rather than in culture and are replete in the New Testament.⁹ These scriptural claims were expounded on incrementally and polemically throughout church history, from as early as John Chrysostom in the late fourth century to Protestant reformers such as John Calvin in the sixteenth century, culminating in the doctrinal classification of complementarianism by the end of the twentieth century.¹⁰

The concept of biblical (or evangelical) egalitarianism—originally a Christian form of feminism—has its roots in the Renaissance and the Reformation. Christine de Pizan was an educated and well-written woman from France in the fourteenth and fifteenth centuries.¹¹ Amidst fending for herself as a widowed mother of three, she used her privilege and voice through writing to advocate a Catholic (possibly more humanistic) moral, intellectual, and social defense for women’s intrinsic value and merits.¹² Pizan seeded the idea that women should be viewed equally to men in being educated, innovative, and virtuous, and that women should strive for it—not implying they were wholly deprived but that they were rarely, if ever, considered.¹³ Two hundred years later, in the 1600s, the Quaker movement appeared as the next significant step in this progression; more specifically, “the writings of early Quaker women” were what “inspired feminist scholars.”¹⁴ One such particular woman, Margaret Fell, published a biblical defense of women’s coequality and right to public ministry, underpinning the cumulative arguments for modern evangelical egalitarianism.¹⁵ Her pamphlet, “Women’s Speaking Justified, Proved and Allowed of by the Scriptures,” explicitly argues that women preaching and ministering, no different than their male counterparts, is espoused in Scripture, and she rebuts the commonly

⁹ John Piper, “A Vision of Biblical Complementarity Manhood and Womanhood Defined according to the Bible,” in *Recovering Biblical Manhood & Womanhood: A Response to Evangelical Feminism*, ed. John Piper and Wayne Grudem (Wheaton, Illinois: Crossway, 2021), 40.

¹⁰ St. John Chrysostom, “Homilies on Galatians, Ephesians, Philippians, Colossians, Thessalonians, Timothy, Titus, and Philemon,” in *Nicene and Post-Nicene Fathers Series I, Volume 13*, ed. Philip Schaff, (Grand Rapids, MI: Wm. B. Eerdmans), <https://ccel.org/ccel/schaff/npnf113/npnf113.i.html>. John Calvin, *Commentaries on the Epistles to Timothy, Titus, and Philemon*, trans. Rev. William Pringle, (Grand Rapids, MI: Christian Classics Ethereal Library), <https://www.ccel.org/ccel/calvin/calcom43/calcom43.i.html>.

¹¹ Marianna Stell, “Christine de Pizan, Professional Writer and Voice for Women in the Middle Ages,” *Library of Congress Blogs*, August 30, 2023, <https://blogs.loc.gov/bibliomania/2023/08/30/christine-de-pizan/>.

¹² Susan Groag Bell, “Christine de Pizan (1364-1430): Humanism and the Problem of a Studious Woman,” *Feminist Studies* 3, no. 3/4 (1976): 175-176, <https://doi.org/10.2307/3177735>.

¹³ *Ibid.*, 177-179.

¹⁴ Sally Bruyneel, “Margaret Fell; Historical Context and the Shape of Quaker Thought,” *Quaker Religious Thought* 95, Article 4 (2000): 25, <https://digitalcommons.georgefox.edu/qrt/vol95/iss1/4>. Jacqueline Broad, “Margaret Fell,” *The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy* (Summer 2024 Edition), <https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/sum2024/entries/margaret-fell/>.

¹⁵ Broad, “Margaret Fell.”

cited complementarian passages.¹⁶ She makes several points in stating her case, but her principal argument can be summarized in three: First, starting in Genesis 1-3, God makes no distinction between man and woman in image, blessing, and dominion, nor sending the serpent-crushing male Seed through a woman, nor calling His male and female covenant people by the feminine form of woman, daughter, and bride, nor speaking and ministering through His male and female covenant people. Second, in the Gospel accounts, Jesus received, taught, honored, and commissioned women, a pattern continued in the NT where women taught, prophesied, and labored alongside men in the gospel. Third, given that the indwelling and empowerment of the Holy Spirit is not restricted by sex, this means Christ can and does speak through women, and no one has the right to silence or resist the work of God through Christ's Spirit in them. Thus, the concept of biblical egalitarianism is the understanding and position that, according to Scripture, women are ontologically equal to men and should be treated as such, and that, in Christ, there is no longer an eminent distinction in roles and functions or hierarchical order among them.¹⁷

At its outset, what became complementarianism was not novel; it was a straightforward reading, interpretation, and implementation of Scripture regarding the cooperative dynamic between man and woman. Unlike the cultural backdrop of the Greco-Roman world, Christian men and women are coequal in worth and status in their humanness and in Christ, yet distinct in some roles and functions, imaging the tri-unity of the Godhead in coequality and mutual distinction.¹⁸ The coining of “complementarian” as a doctrinal category was meant to recapture the balance and beauty of this reality, the symmetry of differences. God's design is that men and women complement one another by reflecting His transcendent value and effectual order in the dignity of each other's distinct personhood, the union and unity of the family, and the polity of the church (which is the household of God).¹⁹

As the centuries passed, history records how this complementary ideal was not always upheld honorably by the Church. The longstanding disparity and denigration of women, as the annals of women's studies attest, were the antecedents to feminism arising from a biblical-Christian basis. While the Church was not the chief propagator of this behavior, it was

¹⁶ Margaret Fell, *Womens Speaking Justified, Proved and Allowed of by the Scriptures*, (London, 1666), accessed June 2026, <https://digital.library.upenn.edu/women/fell/speaking/speaking.html>.

¹⁷ Biblical egalitarianism's Scripture reference examples: Genesis 1:26-28; Luke 24:33-53, John 4:27-42, Acts 1:14-18, Galatians 3:27-28, Colossians 4:12-19, Revelation 1:5-6; 5:9-10.

¹⁸ The Father, the Son, and the Holy Spirit are equal in essence as God while distinct in divine personhood and certain functions—e.g., the sending *from* the Father, the incarnation *of* the Son, the indwelling *of* the Spirit.

¹⁹ Piper, “A Vision of Biblical Complementarity,” 36-38, 63-64.

complicit enough because it possessed the truth of God and failed to honor women accordingly. The Body of Christ was supposed to lead the way, reflecting its exemplar in how to treat, uplift, empower, and enfranchise women in the family, the church, and society. Instead, its failure gave cause for protest and advocacy to correct the malfeasance of male bias and domination, not for female supremacy or the supplanting of men, but for applied equality. Therefore, biblical-Christian feminism (later, egalitarianism), at its outset, was a return to the heart of Scripture's teaching on women's coequality with men and a challenge to its misapplication and misrepresentation.²⁰

Complementarians see God's inherent dignity and value of male-female *through* cooperative order as the priority.²¹ They honor God's design of dignity and distinction between man and woman, and submit to His divine order for the good. Egalitarians see God's inherent dignity and value of male-female *through* shared equality as the priority.²² They honor God's design of dignity and unification in Christ between man and woman, and submit to His new creation of believers for the good. At the core, neither is wrong. However, what they deduce and then emphasize as priority is where they diverge.

The Binary Structural Problems and Need for Change

On paper, complementarianism and egalitarianism are not diametrical positions. They share a common foundation in the image of God—an intrinsic, undiminishable dignity and value as male and female—and the newness in Christ—an equality in status and relevance as children of God, disciples of Jesus, vessels of the Holy Spirit, and the priesthood of believers. Denny Burk, a complementarian scholar, asserts that both are “evangelical” and “wish to honor the authority of Scripture,” even to the extent of differentiating liberal theology and egalitarianism.²³ Kevin Giles, an egalitarian scholar, affirms that “egalitarians would agree with complementarians that although the term “complementary” is not found in the text of Gen 1 the idea is unmistakably present.”²⁴ Where they differ is in what they deduce from this

²⁰ Gretchen Gaebelein Hull, “Biblical Feminism: A Christian Response to Sexism,” *Priscilla Papers* 5, no. 3 (1991): 1-2. <https://jstor.org/stable/community.30700367>.

²¹ The Danvers Statement, Affirmations #2.

²² “Statement on Men, Women, and Biblical Equality,” CBE International, accessed June 2026, https://www.cbeinternational.org/primary_page/statement-men-women-and-biblical-equality/.

²³ Denny Burk, “The Roles of Men and Women,” The Gospel Coalition, accessed June 2026, <https://www.thegospelcoalition.org/essay/the-roles-of-men-and-women/>.

²⁴ Kevin Giles, “The Genesis of Equality,” in *Old Testament Women*, *Priscilla Papers* 28, no. 4 (2014): 4, <https://jstor.org/stable/community.30046568>.

foundation—i.e., complete equality versus complementary equality. Consequently, by the end of the twentieth century, the lines were drawn. The two classifications were entrenched as opponents. The establishment of the CBMW and CBE officially substantiated this centuries-long contention and subsequently created a rippling polarization.

For the past thirty years, your view of what women can and cannot do in the family and the church has hedged you in one of the two camps, whether or not you fully ascribe to the position. In fairness to both, given the implications of the fall in the Garden and its ensuing ramifications across history, a counterbalance to each position was inevitable. Furthermore, fortifying a theological position is neither sinful nor selfish, unless that position is plainly prohibited or denounced in Scripture—e.g., sexual immorality (1 Thess. 4:3-8), the denial of Jesus' Incarnation (2 John 1:7-11). Procuring the right doctrine matters because false teachings abound. Hence, doctrines need to be exegetically clarified and then defended, corrected, or renounced. Nevertheless, regarding a non-salvific issue, the involuntary pigeonholing into one position and labeling (sometimes targeting) if you fail to align is problematic because it's fallacious and causes undue harm.

First, the binary complementarian-egalitarian classifications initiate a version of the “false dilemma” fallacy.²⁵ Not every Christian fits squarely on either side. Many have been drafted into a battle they did not choose and may not agree with. Furthermore, some Christian women make no claim and have no desire to serve in the office of elder, but they do want to fulfill their callings in Christ and utilize the gifts God has given them for His glory and the edification of the Church. To which side do they belong, and would the side change if their gifts and callings were teaching, shepherding, leading, or apostleship (i.e., missions/missionary)? There are Christian husbands who value and treat their wives as co-leads, practicing mutual submission, modeling servant leadership, and teaching their kids the same. There are moms and grandmoms who are welcomed as spiritual mentors by their adult sons, grandsons, and other younger men. Where do these men and women fit? There are churches whose doctrine and practice are male-only eldership, but they have women who lead and teach in various capacities, including in co-ed settings. What side are they? Positing these two classifications as the catch-all for the biblical view and practice of the man-woman dynamic in the family and the church has

²⁵ The “False Dilemma” or “False Dichotomy” fallacy is when an argument wrongly restricts a complex issue to a limited set of options, often only two, creating an either/or, while ignoring other relevant alternatives, qualifications, or degrees between them.

created an unnecessary predicament, leading some to part ways over this false dilemma—believer to believer, believers to churches, and churches to denominations. Granted, some separation is warranted and welcomed, and some are for unrelated reasons, but not all of these instances qualify, and the division could have been avoided.

Second, this false dilemma has aided the “hasty generalization” fallacy with some groups of complementarians and egalitarians.²⁶ The oft-disputed complementarian argument is male headship in marriage and male-only eldership (or pastoral) authority in the church. This is not the fallacy; it is an interpretive conclusion. However, it is this conclusion that abets the “hasty generalization” when it extends beyond the specific role limitations in husbandship and eldership to a broader assumption of women’s roles and authority under men as the defining pattern of male-female relations. For example, when this specific doctrine with a specified context becomes overgeneralized for any context, it then raises several questions about what this means for Christian women scholars, professors, authors, writers, podcasters, professional speakers, business owners, for-profit and non-profit executives, denominational leaders, presidents, etc: Can women not lead, teach, or exercise authority over a man in any role—Christian or non-Christian, beyond the family and the church? Can women not work outside the home, or do so alongside being homemakers? Is a woman selfish or sinful for not wanting marriage or children? If women serve as leaders in their church, should their team or ministry be women-only, or should their leadership be recognized only by women? If a woman teaches in college or a breakout session at a conference, is she only to teach women? Should men never be taught by, learn from, or be led by qualified or gifted women? Should men never read women authors or watch content where women are explaining or expounding upon Scripture or Christian-related topics? Giles observes a clear logical connection to this overreach, suggesting it is not a leap but an inevitable destination.

“If women’s subordination is predicated on the subordination of the first woman before the Fall, then all women are subordinated to all men. Women’s subordination cannot be limited solely to marriage and the church. It is prescriptive for all of creation.... The complementarian argument that women’s creation-based subordination only applies to marriage and the church is entirely novel and counter to their own most fundamental theological premise...”²⁷

²⁶ The “Hasty Generalization” fallacy occurs when an argument infers a general, sometimes broader, claim from very little evidence or a small sample size that is insufficient to sustain that inference.

²⁷ Giles, “The Genesis of Equality,” 6.

Though complementarianism, as defined by CBMW, the Danvers and Nashville statements, and the early works of its designers, does not include or concede this broader inference or application, it is nonetheless the bedrock of the hasty generalization fallacy by some complementarians.

Likewise, for egalitarians, the oft-disputed argument is the exact opposite: since men and women are equal as image-bearers and new creations in Christ, authority, gifting, and ministry (offices, roles, and functions) are no longer determined by gender; they are equally shared. This, too, is not a fallacy but an interpretive conclusion. Similarly, their conclusion also abets a “hasty generalization.” For them, it is when it moves from a biblically-based equality—in God’s image, in Christ redemptively, in His Body with His gifts, and in the family—to the eduction that all male-female role distinctions are fallen, patriarchal, misread, culturally bound, or invalid. For example, what starts with gender equality because of Jesus, when overgeneralized to any context, becomes a panorama of inclusivity. “Affirming” churches and teachings are hermeneutically linked to egalitarianism, using the same equality hermeneutic to relativize or override texts historically understood as establishing fixed male-female distinctions and sacred sexuality in order to make their case for the inclusivity of LGBTQ+ beliefs, normalcy, and ordination.

Jakobus M. Vorster explains how

“Galatians 3:28 has been prominent in liberationist, feminist, post-colonial and critical theory readings of the Bible over the last 30 years... It has often been cited in church debates about slavery and racial discrimination, the ordination of women in churches, gay and lesbian matters and as the motivation for the equality of all people.”²⁸

To be clear, biblical egalitarianism does not entail “affirming” theology. There are evangelical egalitarians who hold a traditional sexual ethic.²⁹ Moreover, CBE has published material arguing that belief in women’s equality does not require acceptance of LGBTQ+

²⁸ Jakobus Vorster, “The Theological-Ethical Implications of Galatians 3:28 for a Christian Perspective on Equality as a Foundational Value in the Human Rights Discourse,” *In die Skriflig/In Luce Verbi* 53, no. 1 (2019), <https://doi.org/10.4102/ids.v53i1.2494>.

²⁹ Sarah Sumner, “Gender,” in *Evangelical Dictionary of Theology*, 3rd ed., ed. Daniel J. Treier and Walter A. Elwell, (Grand Rapids, MI: Baker Academic, 2017), 338.

practices.³⁰ Yet, egalitarianism is the springboard of this hasty generalization fallacy when its proponents draw an all-inclusive conclusion about gender, sexuality, and roles.³¹

The binary complementarian-egalitarian classifications rouse these kinds of hasty generalizations because they, unfortunately and maybe unknowingly, facilitate a false dilemma that treats both as exhaustive, uniform categories, leading to circular interpretations and broad, biased conclusions. Given these two fallacies and the undue harm that follows, a contrarian could use Jesus' and Paul's warnings in Matthew 16:11-12, Galatians 5:7-10, and 1 Corinthians 5:6-8 about the spread and devastating impact of a little leaven on the whole lump to implicitly caution and correct both positions. Hence, the need to move beyond the binary structure and offer a more versatile framework for our multi-dimensional male-female dynamic.

A Proposal of Reclassification to a Four-Quadrant Framework

Getting to the point we are today with complementarianism and egalitarianism has been an evolving process, with the concepts becoming more crystallized and the terms developing across centuries. Thus, for those who may contend against a reclassification, I ask you: Why should we expect that these two are the final forms? There is precedent in the unfolding of God's progressive revelation in Scripture and the development of doctrinal orthodoxy throughout church history, via councils and polemical writings, that while God's truth and Scripture's context are unchanging, our interpretive understanding is not. This is not to say there are multiple interpretations of a text. Rather, our understanding broadens through the diligent, humble process of sound exegesis, and then our doctrinal positions are either reinforced, revised, or rejected.

Currently, complementarianism and egalitarianism are not expansive enough to compensate for the question of Scripture's indeterminacy on this subject and the subsequent practical nuances. Therefore, I propose this binary structure be reworked into a four-quadrant framework, developed from the contrasting basis in the complementarian-egalitarian argument. Introducing a four-quadrant framework is not new. In the *Journal for Biblical Manhood and Womanhood*, Fall 2007 edition, Denny Burk and Jim Hamilton present a frame centered around

³⁰ Catherine Clark Kroeger, "Does Belief in Women's Equality Lead to an Acceptance of Homosexual Practice?," in *Correcting Misunderstandings, Priscilla Papers* 18, no. 2 (2004): 3-10, <https://www.jstor.org/stable/community.30700316>.

³¹ Smothers, "Egalitarianism and the Open-and-Affirming Position." Denny Burk, "Does the Evangelical Egalitarian Spectrum Include Those Who Affirm Gay Marriage?," *Denny Burk* (blog), February 19, 2018, <https://www.dennyburk.com/does-the-evangelical-egalitarian-spectrum-include-those-who-affirm-gay-marriage/>.

hierarchy in principle/no principle and hierarchy in practice/no practice.³² Nevertheless, they dispel three of the four in favor of classic complementarianism, thereby presenting an inconsequential framework, resuming the false dilemma fallacy—either you are our standard of complementarian (hierarchy in principle *and* in practice), or you are biblically wrong. Ergo, the need for reworking. In this case, it is not for the biblical justification of one, but for better substantiation of what Christians biblically believe about this subject.³³

The framework I propose is as follows: On the horizontal axis, left to right, is Distinction–Non-Distinction, and on the vertical axis, top to bottom, is Limitation–Open. “Distinction” refers to the interpretive conclusion that there are God-created biological and authoritative boundaries between men and women in the family and the church. “Non-Distinction,” as the other interpretive end, means there are no sociological and spiritual boundaries between men and women; they are wholly coequal. “Limitation” refers to the interpretive conclusion that there are some roles, offices, and functions not permitted for women because of a God-designed order—mainly, headship in the family, eldership (pastoral ministry) in the church, teaching/preaching before the congregation, and teaching or exercising authority over men in the church. “Open,” as the other interpretive end, means that any role, office, and function are open to women—in the family, they are partners in leading; in the church, no office, role, or function is off-limits to them. These horizontal and vertical axes frame the biblical boundaries of this argument. The four quadrants of this frame are:

1. Top Left: Distinct + Limit (DL) = within coequality, there is God-designed distinction and limitation.
2. Bottom Left: Distinct + Open (DO) = within coequality, there is God-designed distinction with open-limits—*distinction* entails a margin (limit); *open* entails accessibility.
3. Top Right: Non-Distinct + Limit (NDL) = biology aside, there is God-designed equality and freedom with no distinction or imposed limitations, but there is a willing deference—an agreed willingness to yield authority to the man.
4. Bottom Right: Non-Distinct + Open (NDO) = biology aside, there is God-designed equality and freedom with no distinction or limits anywhere.

³² Denny Burk and Jim Hamilton, “Younger Evangelicals and Women in Ministry: A Sketch of the Spectrum of Opinion,” *Journal for Biblical Manhood and Womanhood* 12, no. 2 (2007): 27.

³³ Biblical justification for any doctrinal position is wholly warranted. This paper simply concedes that these positions have biblical arguments for and against them and it is not under its purview.

Figure 2.1

Within this four-quadrant framework, there is room for additional approaches beyond the binary complementarian-egalitarian classifications, without exceeding either. Moreover, these quadrants better identify where differing interpretations situate and can cooperate as family in Christ and partners in ministry. I propose five interpretive positions that are subsumed within this framework. Four of the five are neologisms, constructed primarily by fleshing out the ranges of complementarianism and egalitarianism. I chose to keep complementarianism as a position over egalitarianism because the former has more gradation than the latter. The proposed positions are (with *complementarian* included to see where and how it fits):

TERM	VIEW ON WOMEN	BRIEF DESCRIPTION
Auxiliarian – (Support-Only position)	coequal, distinct, under male headship, only supportive	Both are coequal; women are free to serve but always in support (or subordinate) offices and roles under God-ordained male authority (1 Cor. 11:2-12; 14:34-35).
<i>Complementarian</i> – (Complement position)	<i>coequal, distinct, free under male headship</i>	<i>Both are coequal; men are called to fill headship and eldership, and women are free to serve and lead in certain roles and functions—i.e., non-pastoral, non-congregational preaching, and non-authoritative or teaching over men (1 Tim. 2:8-3:13).</i>
Collaboratarian –	coequal, distinct, under	Both are coequal; men are called to fill headship and

(Co-Labor position)	male headship as co-laborers	eldership, yet men and women can co-labor together in an orderly way in all other roles and functions (2 John)—e.g., women can lead integrated ministries or teach in congregational or mixed adult settings.
Partnerian – (Equal-Partner position)	coequal, no distinction, fully functional partners with willing deference	Both are coequal; women can do any role or function, but there is a willing deference to a male headship-partnership, either in the home or in both the home and the church (Rom. 16:3-5a)—e.g., women pastors/elders, but not the senior pastor.
Coequalitarian – (Full-Equality position)	coequal, no distinction, complete equivalence	There are no distinctions between men and women; thus, no limitations for women (Gal. 3:27-28).

Table 1

These interpretive positions are graphed in the four-quadrant framework as such:

Figure 2.2

In the top-left DL quadrant is auxiliarian and complementarian. In the bottom-left DO quadrant is collaboratarian. In the top-right NDL quadrant is partnerian. In the bottom-right NDO quadrant is coequalitarian. These four quadrants recognize and categorize the interpretive variations within complementarianism and egalitarianism, thereby expanding the binary structure to graph exegetically viable positions while identifying what distinguishes them.

The binary classifications are simply too restrictive for other views. Proponents on both sides acknowledge that some in their respective groups are the opposite “in practice,” indicating

the classification they claim is not what they practice. Burk and Hamilton open their journal entry stating this very fact,

“On the one hand, many people who claim to be complementarian in principle overlap with egalitarians in terms of their practice.² On the other hand, some prominent egalitarian writers have begun to use the term “complementarian” to describe egalitarian positions.³ For this reason, Russell D. Moore has suggested that complementarians might want to trade in the moniker “complementarian” for a term that is more descriptive of their view of gender-hierarchy.⁴”³⁴

The benefit of this four-quadrant framework is that it adequately addresses these comments and underlying concerns. The believers who are considered by complementarianism and egalitarianism to be the opposite “in practice” now have a classification for their interpretive position that did not neatly fit in that binary structure. This could alleviate future infighting and clarify who is actually being addressed in denominational or church-affiliation-group debates and decisions on this subject. It could also demystify doctrinal agreement and governing documents for churches, denominations, and church networks on this subject, so that each believer and church knows before they commit or if it is time to leave. Clarity is a good thing, whether the outcome is favorable or unpleasant.

What is happening in the Southern Baptist Convention with Albert Mohler’s recently proposed “Truth and Unity Amendment” is a case study in point. This potential amendment on the pastoral office, title, and all related functions specifically concerns women’s roles—not maliciously, but doctrinally—and, if it was not clear before, it now overtly identifies the SBC as a classic complementarian convention. Consequently, if adopted next year, it will require any church desiring to be in friendly cooperation with the convention to submit “in practice” to it. Hence, this amendment directly addresses any remaining coequalitarian churches in the SBC—such as Saddleback Church, which left in 2024 over its interpretation and practice of women’s roles in ministry—as well as any churches emplaced in a partnerian position. Given the positions and practices of these churches, they will be challenged to cooperate or leave. Furthermore, those who would identify as collaboratarians are also caught in the crossfire, with their practical interpretive implications and liberties now a target. Even though they agree with complementarianism on “distinction,” they differ on “limitation,” as they are more open to women co-laboring in ministry under the authority of their pastor-elders. For better or for worse,

³⁴ Burk and Hamilton, “A Sketch of the Spectrum of Opinion,” 26.

the SBC messengers have drawn a proverbial line in the sand. Regardless of how the 2027 vote turns out, the clarity is conclusive: complementarianism only has room for the DL quadrant—i.e., complementarians and auxiliarians.

The situation in the SBC is but one example. While writing this white paper, the PCA general assembly voted against permitting qualified women to serve as female deacons; that too places them in the DL quadrant.³⁵ On the other side, the Episcopal Church and the Christian Reformed Church in North America also declared a stance on women's roles—in the NDO quadrant—that compelled any other interpretive views to, ironically, stay and submit or leave.³⁶ Yet the bounds of friendly cooperation with a denomination or affiliate group are not the issue, as these parameters are understandable and expected. Rather, it is the narrowness and bifurcation of these binary classifications that generate group unaffiliation for other viable evangelical interpretations. Where do these complementarians and egalitarians go when their only two options no longer welcome them? The proposed four-quadrant framework provides a solution to this interminable impasse, not with another quandary, but with, at best, cognizant room for brotherly association among churches, networks, and denominations, or, at minimum, mutual participation for the complementarian-egalitarian adjacent nomads.

Conclusion: Where do we go from here?

This paper was not composed to argue for or against complementarianism or egalitarianism, nor to specifically argue for any of the other interpretive positions. Its intent was to present a strong case for moving beyond an insufficient standard of classification without abandoning biblical conviction. Complementarianism and egalitarianism have served a historical and polemical purpose. They arose as necessary responses to real theological and cultural concerns, and neither should be caricatured as inherently unbiblical. At their best, both attempt to preserve something Scripture plainly dignifies: the coequality of men and women before God and in Christ, the practice of Christlikeness in the family, and the mutual edification of the

³⁵ Jon Brown, "PCA General Assembly Votes Against Female Deacons, Advances Report on Christian Nationalism," *Christian Post*, Friday, June 26, 2026, <https://www.christianpost.com/news/pca-votes-on-female-deacons-report-on-christian-nationalism.html>.

³⁶ Canon Erwin M. Soukup, ed., "Dissident Episcopalians Approve 'Affirmation,'" *Episcopal News Service*, September 16, 1977, The Archives of the Episcopal Church, https://digitalarchives.episcopalarchives.org/cgi-bin/ENS/ENSpress_release.pl?pr_number=77297. "Our History," The Christian Reformed Church, accessed June 2026, <https://www.crcna.org/welcome/history>.

Church. Nonetheless, the present binary categories have proven unable to account for the actual range of evangelical interpretation and practice.

The issue, then, is not whether Christians should care about their doctrinal positions or want to get them as closely aligned with Scripture's intent as they can. They should, and must. Nor is the issue whether churches, denominations, and institutions may establish boundaries for fellowship and cooperation. They also should, and must. The issue is whether the inherited prevailing interpretations of the man-woman dynamic accurately capture the positions Christians actually hold with exegetically good reasons. This paper has argued that it does not. By collapsing diverse interpretations into two contested classifications, the current binary structure creates unnecessary suspicion, misidentification, and division. It forces believers, churches, and denominational or affiliational networks to address this multidimensional subject with a two-category option. The four-quadrant framework offered here is not a compromise with theological ambiguity. It is an attempt to prudently position other viable interpretations, neologisms notwithstanding. It preserves the doctrinal concerns embedded in both complementarianism and egalitarianism while permitting the scope of practical interpretive conclusions: distinction or non-distinction, limitation or openness. In doing so, it gives Christians better language for self-identification, better categories for charitable disagreement, and a better tool for determining the real boundaries of brotherly association and mutual participation.

If this proposal were adopted, the framework would not end the debate, but I do believe it would improve it. If rejected, the burden of change remains because the present binary structure will continue to prove inadequate and divisive, and the fallacies of false dilemma and hasty generalization will persist unbothered, all of which without a sensible and prominent solution. However, if the needle moves even minimally, pastors, churches, theological institutions, and scholars should stop treating complementarianism and egalitarianism as exhaustive categories and collectively insist on a broadening beyond these binary classifications within current evangelicalism. If the Church is going to disaffiliate, cooperate, ordain, restrict, or avouch over this issue, then it must do so with more accurate categories. The four-quadrant framework is offered toward that end. Accordingly, I am convinced that the Church can do both on a non-salvific yet consequential biblical subject: stand on biblically-grounded convictions and more accurately classify viable exegetical interpretations to clarify biblical orthodoxy, both for the present day and the future.

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